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1. INTRODUCTION

Interferometric Gravitational Wave (GW) detectors, such as Advanced Virgo, Advanced LIGO and KAGRA [1]–[3], are affected by a variety of noise sources from different physical processes [4]. Among these are mass-density fluctuations that can interact directly with the mirror test masses through gravitational forces leading to the so-called Newtonian noise (NN) [5]–[8]. In particular, NN can be generated by atmospheric density fluctuations and seismic displacements. The best approach to suppress NN noise is through active noise cancellation from the data stream. The rationale is that NN affecting a test mass can be reconstructed by monitoring nearby density fluctuations by means of auxiliary sensors and then using optimally tuned filters to cancel it. Optimizing the positions of the sensors is paramount to maximize the performance of the filters. Since NN can change with time, occasionally requiring new sensor positioning, an approach to this problem is to use an array of mobile seismic sensors that can autonomously move to the optimal positions.

GW experiments span over large surfaces. For example, Virgo is an "L" shape with equal arms, each 3 km long. At the vertices of the "L" there are three large experimental halls housing the vacuum chamber system which encloses the laser beam path, the suspended mirror test masses and optical benches, the electronic modules for control and monitoring, countless signal and power cables, and much more. Roughly speaking, the surface area of each Virgo's experimental hall is around 500 m². Ideally, the robotic sensors should be able to move autonomously throughout these areas, avoiding or overcoming obstacles such as vacuum chambers, racks, cables laid on the floor, etc. Individual robots should then communicate with a control unit that provides them with the coordinates of the positions they need to reach. Once in position, each robot must "deploy" the seismic sensor (ensuring good contact with the floor) and start data acquisition. The acquired seismic data must be synchronized with all other detector data and integrated in real-time into the same data stream. The seismic data must be read in real-time by the control unit, which processes it to produce new positions if necessary, thus completing the operational cycle. Repositioning of the robot array occurs periodically to follow variations in the local seismic field. The typical interval for such occurrences, and thus the duration of a single seismic data acquisition, is on the order of a few hours. It is essential to ensure adequate power autonomy, including a docking station where each robot can autonomously recharge its battery at the end of its operational cycle.

For this purpose, a pilot project called Flexible Grid Mapping Tool (FGMT) is being carried out at the Virgo interferometer site with the collaboration of the European Gravitational Observatory and the Gran Sasso Science Institute. The FGMT is part of the European research project AHEAD-2020.

This conceptual project addresses a number of technological challenges that require large-scale resources. In the FGMT pilot project, the conceptual design is implemented on a smaller and simplified scale. The number of robotic units is reduced to the minimum necessary to demonstrate the principle of operation, namely three units. This also helps to reduce implementation costs. The operational area is a 50m² space within a technical building of the Virgo interferometer. Similarly, the typical duration of data acquisition is adjusted to the average autonomy of the actual robots, and is therefore limited to a few tens of minutes. Despite these limitations, FGMT demonstrates the feasibility of the conceptual project, provided the necessary resources are available in the future.

This report describes the FGMT project, focusing on the technical choices and their implementation. The document also includes a discussion of the challenges encountered and the strategies adopted to

address them, as well as any simplifications or components that were not fully realized. The goal is to provide a guideline for more in-depth future versions of this project.

The document is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the system architecture. Sections 3, 4, and 5 focus on the functionality and hardware implementation of the three FGMT functional units, namely the Mobile Unit, the Data Unit, and the Control Unit, respectively. Section 6 presents the final results, while Section 7 summarizes the project outcomes, key remarks, and future prospects.

Following the final section, you will find links to the other project deliverables, as well as papers and public documents related to this project, and the names of authors and contributors.

The Appendix contains installation details and troubleshooting experience with the electronics.

2. FGMT SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND LOGIC

The FGMT project foresees the realization of three smart robotic platforms - herein called simply *robots* - each carrying a seismic sensor suited for low noise and low frequency observations. The target frequency bandwidth for the sensor is 1 Hz to 100 Hz, as dictated by the typical range of influence of NN in current 2nd generation GW detectors and the next 3rd generation detectors [10,11,12,13].

Each robot has to autonomously move and position itself inside the assigned test area, avoiding obstacles and managing floor imperfections like uneven or slippery surfaces or cables on the floor. A control software computes the assigned positions and transmits them to the robots wirelessly. The repositioning of the robots can take a few minutes. The robots move to positions with an accuracy of a few tens of centimeters; once in position, each robot deploys the seismic sensor assuring good mechanical contact with the floor, then starts the acquisition of seismic data and transfers the data wirelessly to the control software. Upon need, robots should move to a docking station for battery charging. Seismic data from all robotic units must be synchronous among themselves and with the Virgo data system, and be accessible by the control software through an on-line server. A timing accuracy better than 1 ms per day is needed in order to resolve the propagation delay of seismic waves with a speed of 100 m/s throughout a 1 m sensor separation array.

The FGMT architecture, designed to implement the logic just described, is presented in Figure 1. The FGMT is composed of three main functional units: the Control Unit (CU), the Mobile Unit (MU) and the Data Unit (DU). The CU is a cloud-based system that collects the data from the sensors installed on the robots, including the physical coordinates of each unit, and periodically processes the data to produce new optimized positions for the placement of the robots. The optimization process is based on a procedure already developed for optimal sensor positioning and NN cancellation [9]. The MU is the mobile part of the robot, it includes the support frame, the seismic sensor, plus all the electro-mechanical needs and the software implementing the robot navigation. Specifically, the MU hardware components are integrated into one dedicated electronic board, called Mobile Unit Board (MUB). The DU is in charge of reading and digitizing the seismic sensor signal and of the wireless transmission of the data to and from the MU and the CU. Specifically, the DU hardware components are integrated into one dedicated electronic board, called Data Unit Board (DUB).

While there is just one instance of the CU, several instances of the MU and DU may exist. One MU and one DU are assembled together to form one Robot.

Figure 1. FGMT system architecture

3. MOBILE UNIT

The mobile unit fulfills multiple roles: it provides the chassis (hereafter called “the frame”) for mounting all hardware components which also includes a pivot-leg mechanism for stabilizing the robot during data acquisition. The MU also integrates the electromechanical systems and software necessary for navigation operations. Also part of the MU is the docking station for recharging the robots.

3.1 THE FRAME

The frame is the backbone of the MU which carries all the hardware components. The first implementation adopted a wooden frame, as shown on the left of Figure 2. The frame was then redesigned in order to achieve better rigidity and compactness. An important requirement in the redesign process is that the material and thickness of the frame have to guarantee mechanical rigidity but also a light weight. Iron was ruled out as it is more exposed to possible deterioration, whereas aluminum is more difficult to shape. After testing, the choice fell on 1.5 mm thick steel. A picture of the new frame is shown on the right of Figure 2. The assembled robot has a size of 25 × 25 × 12 cm and a weight of about 3 kg of which 17% is the frame. The robot size was kept sufficiently small to move easily through the crowded Virgo experimental areas.

Figure 3 shows a layout of the frame and its accessories. Two rubber wheels, with a diameter of 10 cm, are driven by a pair of DC-g geared motors mounted on the rear of the frame. An omni-directional spherical wheel is installed at the front on the frame’s bottom side to act as a passive caster. Infra-red (IR) proximity sensors are used for the positioning and movement of the unit: an array of analog IR sensors used for the line follower are installed at the front on the frame bottom, while for obstacle recognition, three IR digital sensors are placed on the front and on the two sides of the robot unit.

Two decks are installed on the frame. The lower deck hosts the mentioned DC-motor drivers, the MUB, the battery and the seismic sensor. The battery position on the frame is chosen to guarantee good

stability during seismic measurements. The upper deck (shown in the bottom-left of Figure 3) hosts the DUB. The seismic measurement requires a good connection of the accelerometer with the concrete floor. The solution adopted is a three-point contact with the floor by means of two fixed and one retractable pivot. The retractable pivot acts as a "leg" whose movement is controlled by a servomechanism managed by a signal generated from the MU: the leg is lifted off the ground during the robot's cruise operation, while it is lowered during the seismic data acquisition.

Figure 2: The first wooden frame prototype robot (top left) and three views of one of the final robots (top right, bottom left and bottom right).

Figure 3: Layout of the frame.

3.2 THE NAVIGATION STRATEGY

The robotic units aim to move in experimental halls in presence of mostly fixed obstacles. Inside these areas several local sources, such as pump motors and air ventilation systems, contribute to the overall seismic wave field. The adopted robot navigation strategy relies on autonomous driving, utilizing the line follower technique and motor control practices.

A sketch of the designed setup is shown in Figure 4. A main path, called *Main Pattern (MP)*, is drawn on the floor of the experimental area. The MP is marked with the assistance of white adhesive PVC stripes with a black 2 cm wide line in the middle. Robots can leave the MP and enter predefined *Areas of Interest (Aoi)*, demarcated on the external part of the MP. Additional sets of black and white stripes, properly placed along the MP, constitute barcodes that uniquely identify each Aoi and charging stations, into which each robot will navigate with a motor encoder-based positioning technique. Figure 5 shows the setup developed inside the 1500W experimental building at EGO.

Figure 4. Sketch of the setup and the navigation scheme. The sketch illustrates: the main track (black rectangle) with the global reference system (red) and bar-code markers alongside; a few areas of interest (blue rectangles) with their own local reference system (black arrows), the charging stations (C.S); three navigating robots.

Figure 5. The test setup inside the EGO 1500W experimental building.

The robots navigation plan includes the management of many tasks in order to serve all desired functionalities. Each robot unit shall navigate to desired locations, commanded by the DU. While moving along the main path, the robot shall recognize when it is passing over the commanded barcode and exit the MP, in order to enter the commanded AoI and make its way towards the specific location, traveling the x and y coordinates given by the CU. For the navigation to be considered completed, once in position the robot shall extend its leg and initiate the data acquisition, after which the robot shall return to the MP, waiting for a new command from the CU. Obstacle avoidance is also part of the navigation plan, therefore maneuvers for avoiding collisions must be handled by the robot units. Furthermore, the navigation plan includes the handling of battery recharging by means of approaching the charging station. The robot units must be aware of the status of their own battery level and, upon needs, interrupt their ongoing task in order to drive towards the charging station.

The implementation of these tasks was done with simple and common practices. A breakdown of the navigation goals into basic subtasks is the following:

- line following cruise;
- recognition of the AoI;
- driving straight a given distance inside the area;
- making on spot turns;
- obstacle avoidance;
- leg settling;
- recharge batteries.

Hereafter is a description of how all tasks are managed and how the basic subtasks contribute to the fulfillment of the goals.

3.2.1 Line following cruise

For the line following cruise the robot uses an array of IR sensors. Based on the level of light reflected from either the black or the white region of the stripe, a mapping of the position of the robot with respect to the center of the stripe is made. A classic PID control is then adopted in order to make the robot comply with the line following. The desired position of the robot is set to be the mapped value of the sensors when the robot stays in the middle of the stripe, whilst feedback is given by the actual line sensor measurements. Thus, the error adjusted by the PID gain is fed to the motor actuator.

3.2.2 Recognition of the area of interest

While cruising along the MP, the robots can be commanded with a CU request to reach a desired location inside an AoI. This CU request consists of the triplet (ID, X, Y), where ID is the unique identifier of the AoI, and X and Y are the coordinates of the desired location inside that AoI. The aforementioned information is transferred from the Raspberry Pi (DU) via Inter-Integrated Circuit (I2C) serial protocol in the form of an interrupt.

The IR array is also used for the identification of the location of areas of interest and of the charging station. Different combinations of IR sensors in the array are used for this purpose. The identification procedure takes place with the assistance of dedicated sets of black and white stripes resembling a *bar-code*. These sets are placed on the side of the main track stripe and perpendicular to it, close to each AoI (Figure 4). A different number of such black stripes is used to uniquely identify each AoI. While

cruising along the main path the robot reads bar-codes using the outermost IR sensors of the array. When a match is found between the read bar-code pattern and the hard coded pattern of the ID that the robot is instructed to travel to, the robot exits the line following cruise and enters that AoI. Each AoI has a local coordinate reference system onto which the global coordinates of the triplet are transformed, in order for the CU to uniquely identify the position inside the experimental area.

3.2.3 Moving inside the area of interest

As far as the traveling of the robot inside the AoI is concerned, the robot has to perform a combination of the basic tasks of moving straight and making on spot turns. The implementation of these basic movements is achieved by applying a simple PID control. This control gets feedback from motor encoders that provide information about the traveled distance and it results in movements prone to a few centimeter accuracy. The control scheme is focused on making sure that the wheels turn synchronously and by the same amount, thus resulting in accurate movements.

Obstacles avoidance is achieved by the use of the array of IR sensors placed along the robot perimeter and the implementation of an *avoidance maneuver*. The latter consists of a combination of straight driving and on-spot turn to make a “U” shaped maneuver to get around the obstacle and recover the foreseen path.

3.2.4 Leg settling

The seismic measurement requires a good connection of the accelerometer with the floor. The solution adopted is a three-point contact with the floor by means of two fixed and one retractable pivot (see also Section 4.1). The retractable pivot acts as a “leg” whose movement is controlled by a servomechanism managed by the MUB. The leg is lifted off the ground during the robot’s cruise operation, while it is kept extended during the seismic data acquisition. The length of the leg is regulated such that when in the extended position, the seismic sensor attached to the robot’s frame is aligned in the vertical direction. The leg movement is regulated by a continuous rotation servo [27]. Details are provided in the Appendix.

3.2.5 Battery charging

Robots need periodical battery recharging. Each robot routinely reads the battery status through the dedicated hardware. When the battery charging level goes below a given threshold an interrupt is generated and the robot prioritizes a drive to the charging station. That is done by combining the line following practice and the recognition of the charging area through the reading of its unique bar-code pattern (also shown in Figure 4). For battery charging, tests were carried out with an inductive (“contactless”) charging system to facilitate the positioning of the mobile unit. Unfortunately, all available commercial systems tested did not meet the requirement of necessary voltages and currents. We then evaluated a charging system with sliding contacts, but due to time constraints the latter was not implemented.

3.3 THE MOBILE UNIT BOARD

The Mobile Unit Board is the electronic board implementing all the hardware needed for the robot navigation. The MUB components are illustrated in Figure 6, the layout of the board is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Main components of the Mobile Unit Board: (1) ATmega2560 microcontroller; (2) Pulse Width Modulation; (3) Motor drivers; (4) IR sensors; (5) battery level monitor.

Figure 7: Mobile Unit Board, Altium layout.

The MUB's core is a Crumbino-Mega which is based on ATmega2560 microcontroller, chosen for its multiple inputs availability and for signal conditioning and processing. The code for the navigation of the MU is embedded in this controller. Motor drivers are used to control the two motors which pilot the two wheels. Motor drivers functions include powering the motors with the appropriate amount of voltage and current through Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) and reading the motor encoders to determine the traveled distance.

The MUB also implements several interfaces: the connectors for the power supply and communication with the wheel motors and connectors for the infrared proximity (IR) sensors used for the robot navigation. Finally, a 4 cell Li ion battery with 2 Ah capacity and a level monitor circuit are used

respectively to power the various circuits of the board and to generate an interrupt signal when the battery voltage level goes below a given threshold.

Technical implementation details and troubleshooting of the MUB are described in the appendix.

4. DATA UNIT

Data unit functionalities consist of the acquisition of seismic data, their synchronization and the communication with the MU and the CU in order to transfer seismic data and position coordinates.

4.1 THE DATA UNIT BOARD

The data unit functionalities take place in the DUB. The DUB components are illustrated in Figure 8. The layout of the DUB is illustrated in Figure 9.

The DUB's core is a Raspberry Pi 4 model B microprocessor equipped with 8 GB RAM which manages the data acquisition and wireless transmission to the CU.

One high precision external AD/DA extension board is used to digitize the seismometer analog signal. This AD/DA board is based on the 8 channel ADS1256 ADC chip, offering 24-bit resolution and up to 30 kHz sampling frequency.

A GPS disciplined oscillator (GPSDO) module is used to provide a stable clock synchronized with the Virgo detector signals. Indoor reception of the GPS signal requires equipping the test room with a GPS repeater and equipping each DUB with a passive GPS antenna connected to the GPSDO.

The DUB also manages power and conditioning of the seismic sensor whose connectors are integrated in the board. The selected seismic sensor is the Wilcoxon model 731- 207 accelerometer [26], preferred for its low intrinsic noise and acceptably small weight and size. However, a wide variety of low frequency and low noise sensors can be integrated by the DUB, such as IEPE accelerometers or pre-polarized microphones and fluxgate or Hall effect magnetometers. In order to read these signals and for antialiasing filtering, two Op-Amps are used. Finally, voltage regulators are implemented on the board in order to convert the battery voltage output into the voltage levels needed by the component downstream.

Figure 8. Main hardware components of the Data Unit Board: (1) Raspberry Pi microprocessor, (2) ADC board, (3) GPSDO, (4) seismic sensor, (5) antialiasing Op-Amps, (6) voltage regulators.

Figure 9. Data Unit Board, Altium layout.

4.2 ACQUISITION OF SEISMIC DATA

The hardware of the system is a Raspberry Pi 4 [21] connected to a commercially available 8-channel 24-bit ADC module [20]. Presently only one ADC channel is used to read the accelerometer signal at 1 kHz sampling frequency. The inherent noise of the acquisition chain, i.e. front-end electronics and ADC channel, has been evaluated. A preliminary measurement shows a $3\mu\text{V}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ flat spectral noise from a few Hz to 100 Hz, which is slightly larger than the accelerometer's inherent noise. Using purpose-designed electronics, a stable +2.5 V offset (the internal ADC voltage reference V_{ref}) is added to the ADC input to allow reading zero-mean value analog signals. Signals are then filtered with a second-order Butterworth low-pass filter for anti-aliasing purposes. Troubleshooting details on this topic are presented in Section 4.5.3.

4.3 SYNCHRONIZATION

To comply with the required timing accuracy of 1 ms/day the ADC built-in 7.68 MHz quartz oscillator, whose measured accuracy was in the range of 1 ppm, had to be replaced with one commercially available GPSDO module with a measured accuracy better than 1 ppb. The use of a GPSDO inside closed environments such as Virgo buildings required the installation of a wireless GPS repeater inside the test room [24] and one GPS antenna receiver connected to the GPSDO of each DUB [25].

A crucial issue has been the synchronization of all data units among them and with the Virgo data system. The GPSDO provides the time beats but not the absolute start time. The first attempted solution has been a software mechanism implementing the NTP protocol. This solution has a few ms reproducibility error which is not satisfactory. The final solution is a more advanced GPSDO module [23] that offers time beats synchronized with the GPS time signal. Troubleshooting details on this topic are presented in Section 4.5.4.

4.4 COMMUNICATION AND DATA TRANSFER

The Raspberry Pi embeds one main software application composed of two threads. The first thread manages the ADC reading (see Section 4.2). The second thread manages the data transfer which is described hereafter.

The FGMT data flow is described in Figure 10. Seismic sensor data from each DU are received by the FrameBuilder, a Virgo proprietary application running on a Linux machine.

Figure 10. FGMT data flow scheme. Red arrows show the position coordinate data flow, black arrows show the sensor data flow, and blue arrows the timing synchronization.

The FrameBuilder packs at run-time the position (from the CU) and sensors data into the Virgo data packet format (called *frame*) and sends them to the Virgo data acquisition database (DAQ). The CU optimization software - which runs on another Linux machine - reads the frame data from the DAQ, processes them, and produces new position coordinates which are sent to the FrameBuilder, then to each DU and finally to each MU. The communication between the DU and the FrameBuilder occurs through TCP sockets. The communication with the MU occurs through I2C protocol. To let robots move freely, data transfer between the DU and the FrameBuilder must occur wirelessly. The WiFi protocol turned out to be the optimal solution, after having evaluated and discarded other options, like the Bluetooth-2.0 offered by Raspberry Pi, which was tested and turned out to have a distance range of a few meters - too short for our purposes, and the LoRa protocol which has a too low throughput rate. Troubleshooting details on this topic are presented in Section 4.5.2.

4.5 DATA UNIT: DESIGN CHOICES, FACED ISSUES AND LESSON LEARNED

4.5.1 The Microcontroller choice

Many of the design choices were driven by previous experiences, which helped reduce software development time. However, with the benefit of hindsight, we might have made different decisions. For instance, as the central unit for data collection, packaging, and transmission, we chose the Raspberry Pi 4B [21] running the Raspbian operating system. However, we quickly encountered challenges related to multi-threading, which is not fully under the programmer's control. To mitigate the phase shifts in the sampled signal, we dedicated an entire core to the data acquisition thread, leaving the other three cores to manage the rest of Raspberry Pi's operations. A potentially better solution would have been to use a bare-metal operating system on the Raspberry Pi. While this approach was tested, it proved too time-consuming, particularly for those without prior experience in this field. Another viable option could have been an mbed microcontroller, such as the Arm Mbed LPC1768 Board NXP [22], which has been successfully used in the past for simpler applications. This microcontroller operates as a real-time system, making it well-suited for accurate timing requirements. Unfortunately, the chosen ADC (see next paragraph) does not provide libraries for this microcontroller, although it does offer a library with documented examples of use with the Raspberry Pi. Additionally, the mbed board lacks onboard Wi-Fi, which poses another limitation for our application.

4.5.2 The communication protocol choice

One reason for choosing the Raspberry Pi was its built-in Wi-Fi capability, which has been our preferred communication protocol from the start. However, from the very first attempts to use the primary Wi-Fi network available at the Virgo site, we encountered significant challenges. The main Virgo site WiFi was not designed for this purpose, and we were ultimately unable to integrate the Raspberry Pi into it. Instead, we succeeded in connecting the Raspberry Pi to the secondary Wi-Fi network. Unfortunately, even this network imposes certain limitations. To explore alternatives, we conducted tests using the Raspberry Pi's built-in Bluetooth capability. However, during these quick preliminary trials, we found this solution unsuitable due to significant limitations: when the Raspberry Pi was obstructed by obstacles such as walls or columns, the communication quality degraded or was interrupted entirely. We also briefly investigated the use of LoRa, a protocol characterized by its long range but low throughput. Due to its limited data transfer capacity, LoRa was deemed unfit for our needs. After evaluating these options, we decided to rely on the secondary Wi-Fi network at the Virgo site for communication.

4.5.3 The ADC board choice

During the initial tests we identified two key limitations of the ADC board:

- It could effectively read only positive values, with a minimum reading threshold of -100 mV.
- The board's software library allowed reading synchronously with the ADC embedded clock only one out of the 8 channels nominally available.

The first limitation was resolved during the FGMT design phase of the DUB by summing a reference voltage from the Waveshare ADC board. The second limitation indeed is not a showstopper, as the FGMT

design required each robot to carry only a single sensor. However, we explored the possibility of enabling synchronous readings from up to four ADC channels, matching the DUB board's input capacity, thus allowing for a potential future expansion. To achieve this, we conducted an in-depth study of the ADS1256 chip and addressed the limitation through a software solution. By modifying the low-level library, we enabled multi-channel synchronous reading. Due to the complexity of this task, a digital analyzer was used to ensure proper timing configuration and validate the solution.

4.5.4 The GPSDO choice

To test the waveshare ADC performances, we compared its reading with a trusted Virgo ADC module when feeding them with the same analog output from one signal generator module. Comparing the two readings we observed phase drifts, which we attributed to the ADC built-in clock generated by a quartz oscillator. To address this issue, we purchased an external GPS disciplined clock generator that interfaces with the Raspberry Pi via one of its four USB ports. This modification cured the phase drifts issue. However, this device has a limitation: it only provides a stable frequency, maintained through a feedback system, but lacks a time reference t_0 — the signal indicating the start of each second. To overcome this, we purchased another GPS disciplined oscillator model [23], which not only provides a stable frequency but also allows to implement a work-around to extract the t_0 information. The devised trick consists in commanding the Raspberry to send a 1Hz square wave to the GPSDO and wait for the transition from 0 to 1 to mark the t_0 . The GPSDO of course required the implementation of one wireless GPS repeater module and GPS receiving antenna system, as described in Section 4.3.

5. CONTROL UNIT

The Control Unit (CU) is a cloud-based system that collects the data from the sensors installed on the robots, including the physical coordinates of each unit, and periodically processes the data to produce new optimized positions for the placement of the robots. The optimization process is based on a machine learning procedure [9] that uses a 2D Gaussian process regression (GPR) and that was already developed for optimal sensor positioning and NN cancellation for the Virgo detector [1]. The optimization code runs on CPUs and the process can be parallelized on a number CPUs selected by the user. At present, NN sensors in the Virgo experimental areas are fixed in place and, if needed, have to be moved by hand one by one to new optimal positions after running the optimization process.

The goal of the optimization is to understand from the physical properties of the seismic field, in particular the two-point correlations between couples of sensors, how to deploy the sensors. The solution takes the form of a surrogate Wiener filter with seismometers as input channels, and whose output constitutes an estimate of the gravity fluctuation produced by the seismic field. The Wiener filter is known to minimize the variance of the residual data, and it was therefore proposed for NN cancellation in GW detectors by passing data from witness sensors through the Wiener filter and its output subtracted from a target channel. The Wiener filter minimizes the residual noise for a given configuration of the seismic array and the goal of the optimization process is to find the optimal locations of the N sensors that minimize the residuals.

Since Virgo's sensitivity is not yet good enough to observe NN, one needs to provide a model of the spatial correlations between the sensors to infer the correlation between the N sensors and the test

mass of the detector. This can be achieved using a Bayesian approach exploiting GPR. The main problem of doing this is that we have to infer a 4D function (the dimension of the space is given by the total number of coordinates of the couples of sensors, i.e., 4) from the cross spectral density of N sensors, which means, inferring a 4D function from $N \times N$ points. Nevertheless, the density of the data points in the 4D space is not enough to infer with sufficient accuracy the values of the spatial correlations on it. Moreover, given the big dimensions of the involved matrices, the GPR would require a high computational cost and time. As a consequence, the code uses GPR only to construct a regular 4D grid on a subset of points and then uses linear interpolation based on this grid to calculate the spatial correlations. This way, the entire optimization process can be handled in a feasible time and output more precise results than using the GPR directly on the $N \times N$ couples of points.

5.1 THE CONTROL UNIT AT WORK

To overcome the issue of manual placing of the sensors at the end of the optimization, the goal of the CU is to automate the process of data acquisition, processing and sending data back to the robot units to create a continuous 2-way process in which the robot units are always in the optimal positions based on the data that they acquired. The optimization code [9] was originally designed to work with the 15+ sensors of the array for NN cancellation but can work for any number of sensors. The main bottleneck is given by the computational time needed for the analysis. In the case of the Virgo array, a full optimization analysis requires up to a few days depending on the amount of data used and on the number of sensors. Even for three sensors only, the computational time can reach several hours.

To face this issue we decided to process 25 minute long segments of data at a time and to reduce the number of steps used in the Gaussian process regression. The latter choice comes with the cost of reducing the accuracy of the optimization, but, with three sensors only, the impact is less significant and therefore acceptable. The choice of the time window to analyze is also dictated by the estimated battery life of the robot units on a full charge, which is approximately 30 minutes. At the end of the data taking period and when data has been correctly acquired, the CU sends a flag to head the units back to the charging station. Therefore, this choice represents the realistic case in which the units collect data until their batteries need recharging.

Using the aforementioned settings, we successfully tested the reading of data from a set of accelerometers installed with the purpose of testing the CU and that are of the same model as those that will be installed on the robots; we ran the optimization code and successfully sent the optimized positions to the data unit which, in its turn, is in charge of sending the results to the robot units.

Despite the successful testing of the 2-way process between the CU and the data unit, we continued to face the limitation of the computational time required by the analysis which is approximately 3 hours with the code running on 8 CPUs to analyze approximately half an hour of data. As a consequence, the robot units would update their optimal positions only every 3 hours. We also verified that the increase of the number of CPUs on which the code runs can mildly improve the performance, but, since we use the working nodes of the Virgo computing farm in which we have to leave a certain number of CPUs free to prevent issues, we decided to not use more than 8. This leads to a possible improvement for future analyses, that is to adapt the code to run on GPUs and test if the computation time decreases. The use of a dedicated computing machine may also improve the performance of the optimization process.

Another limitation that we faced is the fact that we placed the sensors in a building far from the test masses of the detectors, where a NN cancellation array is usually installed to accurately map the noise field that acts on the test masses. This choice was driven by the fact that the experimental buildings

around the test masses are crowded and make the installation of new sensors for test purposes extremely cumbersome, especially during observing runs. In any case, this issue could be easily overcome by setting the origin of the coordinate system used by the optimization code, which must correspond to the position of the test mass, in the middle of the laboratory where the sensors were placed.

5.2 MAPPING THE NOISE ENVIRONMENT

To evaluate and characterize the noise environment in which the robots would operate, we placed three accelerometers on the floor of one Virgo experimental building within a few meters distance from each other. The data acquired by these accelerometers and discussed in this section are the same as those used to test the optimization code and the CU, as mentioned in the previous section. The accelerometers are of the same type as those that will be installed on the robots and, as a consequence, help us to gain an insight of the seismic field that the robot units would map. In particular, the accelerometers collected 2.5 months of data from mid April 2023 until the beginning of June of the same year. For the sake of simplicity, we show only the data from one week that we deem representative of the entire data taking period.

As a first instance, we calculate the coherence between the accelerometers to evaluate up to which frequency the self noise of the sensors is dominant. Being the sensors on the same floor at relatively small distance, we expect that they measure the same seismic background noise which should cause a high degree of coherence (> 0.5). On the other hand, low coherence (< 0.5) indicates that the sensors are reading self noise only, which is not correlated. As a consequence, we calculate the coherence among pairs of sensors and infer that, up to frequencies between 5 Hz and 6 Hz, background seismic noise lies below the sensor self noise (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Coherence calculated between the three accelerometers used to characterize the seismic environment.

Figure 12: 1-week time frequency plots for the three accelerometers. Persistent noise lines and the periodicity of the seismic field are clearly visible as well as some transient noises. We also appreciate how the three sensors measure the same seismic noise without any appreciable difference.

Figure 12 shows a 1-week long time frequency plot for each accelerometer. From these spectrograms, we can already appreciate the fact that the three sensors measure the same seismic field without any appreciable difference. We suppose that this is caused by the fact that they are mostly equally distant from the main noise sources of the experimental building in which they are placed. The periodicity of the seismic noise is also clearly visible as well as the persistent noise lines caused by the air conditioning system. These persistent noise lines are also coincident with the peaks in coherence observable in Figure 12. We also point out the correlation between the seismic noise levels and the days of the week, in fact Monday, May 1 (bank holiday in Italy) and the weekend of May 6,7 show a reduction of the seismic noise levels below 15 Hz. On May 5 a sharp broadband noise source appeared between 1 Hz and 100 Hz and is probably related to activities within the experimental area related to the commissioning of the Virgo detector. A smoother broadband noise source in the same frequency range as the former appears also on May 2 and 3 and we found that it could be related to winds exceeding 40 km/h at the site (Figure 13).

Figure 13: comparison between seismic noise levels in the time-frequency plots with wind speed measured at the site. A clear correlation appears on Mat 2 and 3

Figure 14 also shows the effect of the broadband noise between 1 Hz and 100 Hz caused by wind by comparing the seismic noise spectra calculated during a windy period and during a period in which wind speed is < 10 km/h. From Figure 14 we can also see that the seismic noise measured by the three accelerometers is again mostly the same.

Figure 14: Comparison of the seismic spectra between windy days (speed > 30 km/h) and non windy days (speed < 10 km/h).

In general, we expect that the seismic field measured by the three accelerometers is representative of that of the experimental areas in which the robots would operate.

6. FINAL SEISMIC DATA ACQUISITION TEST

As a final validation test, we acquired two identical seismic sensors. One “reference” sensor, always placed on the ground, was acquired using Virgo's data acquisition system, while the other was mounted on the robot unit acquired by the latter's system.

6.1 PRELIMINARY EVALUATION

The two sensors were preliminarily verified and inter-calibrated by placing them both on the ground. The robot's acquisition system performed as expected, with the seismic spectrum for both sensors being virtually identical. However, it was observed that below a certain frequency (approximately 20 Hz), the noise level of the robot's ADC was higher than that of the system used in Virgo. Additionally, a loss of synchrony between the two systems was noted during long acquisition periods.

This issue was addressed and resolved with a new version of the Raspberry Pi board operating system.

Figure 15: Comparison of the seismic spectra acquired with the two seismic sensors, both placed on the ground. Top are the two spectra (red curve is the reference sensor on the ground, while blue curve is the sensor acquired with the robot system, also placed on the ground); in the middle the transfer function between them (modulus and phase); bottom is the coherence. The phase plot clearly shows the residual delay accumulated by the robot data.

6.2 FINAL EVALUATION

The robot's seismic sensor was then installed on the robot, with the unit placed on its three contact points (leg down) and positioned close to the reference seismic sensor. In this case it was observed that the mechanical resonances of the structure (the frame) altered the frequency response of the sensor, making it no longer comparable to the ground reference sensor.

We believe this issue can be resolved with a new, more rigid structure, which we were unable to implement in this version due to time constraints.

Figure 16: Same comparison as in figure 15, but with the robot sensor placed on the mobile unit. Top are the two spectra (red curve is the reference sensor on the ground, blue is the sensor acquired with the robot system, now placed on the mobile unit); in the middle the transfer function between them (modulus and phase); bottom is the coherence. In the modulus plot the value is no longer flat, indicating the frame resonances mentioned in the text, while in the phase plot it is shown that the delay of the robot unit is significantly reduced.

7. CONCLUSIVE REMARKS AND OUTLOOKS

The FGMT is a pilot project to test the feasibility of mobile seismic sensors for the cancellation of NN at future GW detectors. The project requires sensing units autonomously reaching their positions inside large indoor areas, then measuring low-frequency seismic noise and transferring the data for remote processing. The developed system incorporates Raspberry PI and Arduino micro-controllers with auxiliary electronic components. The navigation strategy implements the line follower technique and motor controlled positioning practices. For the purposes of the project, the CU optimization process was adapted from [9].

The devised system architecture and technical choices were dictated by some effective constraints. The project budget has been underestimated, in fact the funds requested include only 1 year FTE and zero hardware cost. In order to face this issue, the number of robotized units, initially 10, has been reduced to 3, the minimum sufficient number to test the project feasibility.

The technical choices, like for example the navigation strategy based on line follower and motor encoder techniques, have been dictated by the need to reduce costs and to use the already existing expertise at the EGO and GSSI labs.

The project met its principal goals. Three robotic units have been realized. They are proven to navigate autonomously as requested inside the designated test area and reach the assigned positions with order of 10 cm accuracy. As well achieved is the wireless WiFi-based communication and seismic data transmission between each robot and the Virgo computer cluster where the main control software resides. The synchronization of each robot seismic data with the Virgo data system has been achieved successfully by implementing on each robot a GPS disciplined clock wirelessly connected to a GPS repeater unit for distributing the GPS signal indoors.

The control unit carries out its key functions: receiving the seismic data from the robots, running the optimization software to produce optimized positions; and communicating these new positions to the robots. However, these functionalities could not be fully tested on the final setup due to several challenges. The major showstopper is due to the computational time required by the optimization code which proved incompatible (around 3 hours) with the robot's lifetime. This problem was compounded by the impossibility of realising a battery charging system.

However, the battery recharging system was investigated and initial tests were conducted using a system based on inductive charging. Yet the selected component proved not robust enough and repetitively failed. Additionally, the project accumulated a considerable delay due to some unexpected problems: firstly, the difficulty in hiring an expert scientist with competences in the robotic field; then delays in parts procurements and delivery (for example the Crumbino processor is no longer on the market); some commercial components to be replaced (for example the under performing clock of the ADC module); finally the failure of some components (for example the induction coil system).

Looking at future perspectives, the FGMT concept can be improved under many aspects to fulfill the request of next generation GW experiments, like the Einstein Telescope [12] and Cosmic Explorer [13]. Indeed, the NN is expected to be a limiting factor for these detectors to reach their sensitivity goal in the low frequency range (<10 Hz) and an optimizable NN subtraction system shall be employed. To be used in this contest, the reliability of the robotized array will be essential, passing from a functional prototype to a more industrial-like unit. More sophisticated hardware and navigation strategies could be applied, for example adopting LIDAR [18] assisted navigation and embedding feed-forward controls along with the classic PID ones, and possibly A.I. based techniques. Attention shall be placed to reduce and minimize power consumption. The adoption of GPUs for the optimization process will predictably reduce the computational time.

The DU, as it has been designed and implemented, is a versatile and cheap system. It can be easily interfaced and integrated into any data acquisition system and equipped with different kinds of environmental sensors, working as a standalone wireless data acquisition unit. An application of the standalone DU, is the use as a portable multisensor data acquisition unit for mapping the environment of GW detector sites searching for noisy sources, an activity that is usually extensively performed during the detector commissioning phase [17].

The future also foresees the deployment of gravitational wave detectors on the Moon. Among the proposals for such detectors is the Lunar Gravitational Wave Antenna (LGWA) [19], which, although the effects of NN on the Moon are limited, still needs accurate modeling of the Lunar seismic field to optimize GW detection. Unfortunately, current studies of the Lunar seismic field are strongly model dependent and cannot be supported by real data. Therefore, the hypothetical use of a robotized array similar to FGMT, adapted for operating in an alien environment and deployed before LGWA, can reduce the risk of an inaccurate modeling of the Lunar ambient seismic field that could hinder the successful operation of LGWA.

Other applications of the mobile sensor array are envisioned beyond GW experiment sites. Possible uses include mapping environmental noise or ambient parameters in hostile, toxic, or hazardous environments; detecting dust or atmospheric pollutants; and tracking and identifying noise sources.

Links to online project resources

The FGMT project annexes, including video, mobility software code, and control software code, are available at the following link:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/ahead2020robots/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Publications, conferences participation and internal notes related to this project

Giulio Ballardin *et al.*, "A robotized environmental sensor array for gravitational wave observatory sites," *2023 27th International Conference on Methods and Models in Automation and Robotics (MMAR)*, Międzyzdroje, Poland, 2023, pp. 394-399, doi: 10.1109/MMAR58394.2023.10242533.

Mario Graziaplana, [A robotized environmental sensor array for gravitational wave observatory sites](#), *AHEAD 2020 workshop on the synergies between astrophysics and geoscience*, 5 March 2024, European Gravitational Observatory, Cascina, Italy

Irene Fiori, Federico Paoletti, Fabio Bonsignorio, Jan Harms, Maria C. Tringali - Evaluation study of iRobot Roomba Create 2 mechanical response for the requirement definition of a mobile robot platform - Virgo codifier [VIR-0787A-19](#).

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APPENDIX - MUB technical implementation

A.1 MUB microprocessor

The MUB's core is a Crumbuino-Mega, which is based on ATmega2560 microcontroller, chosen for its multiple inputs availability and for signal conditioning and processing (Figure 17). The code for the navigation of the robot units is embedded in this controller. Figure 18 shows all the connections between the board and all the hardware components used for the movement of the robot units. A criticality encountered with this device was its difficult availability. This led to the use of a more commercial Arduino Mega for one of the three robot units despite the poor dimensional and geometric adaptability with the MUB.

Figure 17: Crumbuino-Mega.

Figure 18: Crumbuino-Mega schematic.

A.2 Motors

Motors (Figure 19) are used for the mobility of the wheels. The adopted gearmotor is a powerful 12V brushed DC motor with a 102.08:1 metal gearbox and an integrated quadrature encoder that provides a resolution of 64 counts per revolution of the motor shaft, which corresponds to 6533 counts per revolution of the gearbox's output shaft. The gearbox is composed mainly of spur gears, but it features helical gears for the first stage for reduced noise and improved efficiency. Each motor has six color-coded, 8" (20 cm) leads terminated by a 1x6 female header with a 0.1" pitch, as shown in Figure 19. This header works with standard 0.1" male headers like the ones used in the design of the board. Figure 20 and Table 1 describes the wire connections and functions, respectively.

Figure 19: Metal Gearmotor 37Dx73L mm 12V with 64 CPR Encoder.

Figure 20: Motor header connectors.

Color	Function	Connection on the board
Red	motor power (connects to one motor terminal)	M1OUTA or M2OUTA
Black	motor power (connects to the other motor terminal)	M1OUTB or M2OUTB
Green	encoder GND	GND
Blue	encoder Vcc (3.5V - 20V)	5V
Yellow	encoder A output	A_ENCO_L or A_ENCO_R
White	encoder B output	B_ENCOL or B_ENCO_R

Table 1: Motor header functions.

A.3 Motor Drivers

Motor Drivers (Figure 21) are used in order to control the motors. This includes powering the motors with the appropriate amount of voltage and current through Pulse Width Modulation (PWM), and also reading the encoder of the motors to determine the Robot's traveled distance. More specifically, the design was based on Pololu's Dual VNH5019 Motor Driver Shield for Arduino and its schematic. This driver makes it easy to control two high-power DC motors with an Arduino-compatible board. Its robust dual VNH5019 motor drivers operate from 5.5 to 24 V and can deliver a continuous 12 A (30 A peak) per motor, or a continuous 24 A (60 A peak) to a single motor connected to both channels. These drivers also offer current-sense feedback and accept ultrasonic PWM frequencies for quieter operation. On the board there is one circuit for the left motor and one for the right, shown in Figure 22.

Figure 21: PCB layout of left and right motor driver.

Figure 22: Motor drivers schematic.

A.4 Mobility sensors

Infrared proximity (IR) sensors are used for the positioning and movement of the device. Specifically, for the line following function a Reflectance Sensor Array is used. This array of IR LED/phototransistor pairs is ideal for precise detection of reflectance changes, such as needed for line detection. It operates within a voltage range of 2.9 V to 5.5 V and features adjustable brightness control independent of the supply voltage, along with separate controls for odd and even emitters. In the design of the board a header is used in order to connect 11 sensors of the array, the odd and even selection and to power the sensor (5 Volts and GND). On the PCB layout, first is written the pin of the microcontroller, making it easy to find the right pin for programming, and then the name of the pin on the sensor. For example, D14 – EVN describes that the Even pin of the sensor, used to control even emitters, is connected to the Digital 14 pin (D14) of the microcontroller, A7 – ARR3 means that the third emitter of the array sensor is connected to the Analog 7 pin (A7) of the microcontroller, and so on. The PCB layout and schematic is reported in

Figure 23. The difficulties related to this type of sensor are due to the ambient light that affects the readings of the phototransistors, which are fundamental for positioning control on the MP. By varying the light with which one works, the behavior of a generic robot unit can change slightly during the Line following phase. Furthermore, light reflections interferences between near sensors composing the IR bar must be considered: it was therefore necessary to cover the adjacent photodiode/phototransistor pairs and therefore use only those at the appropriate distance in order to allow the robot units to remain aligned with the MP, minimizing the disturbances.

Figure 23: PCB layout and schematic of line-following sensor.

Additionally, 6 digital distance sensors are used in order to detect nearby obstacles. The digital sensors detect objects between 2 cm and 10 cm (0.8" and 4") away and are powered by 5V power supply. With their quick response time, small size, and low current draw, these sensors are a good choice for non-contact object detection. The user is able to interface with the sensors using a three-pin 0.1" connector. In the board there are many headers in order to connect the sensors with the Crumbuino microprocessor as can be seen in Figure 24.

Figure 24: PCB layout and schematic of digital distance sensor.

The left pin of the headers corresponds to GND, the middle one corresponds to 5V while the right pin corresponds to the output of the sensor. On the PCB layout, first is written the pin of the microcontroller, making it easy to find the right pin for programming, and then the name of the sensor. A simple S corresponds to a digital sensor, while FS corresponds to an analog distance sensor that can eventually be connected to the board. For example, D25 – S describes that a digital distance sensor is connected to the Digital 25 pin (D25) of the microcontroller.

It must be said that, for the purpose of the obstacle avoidance task, 6 digital sensors, positioned in total on the front and rear parts of each robot unit, along the longitudinal and transverse axes, proved to be the minimum necessary to overcome parallelepiped-shaped obstacles, arranged perpendicularly to their motion trajectory, nothing more. Another problem related to this type of sensors is that their range of action proved to be a little too short: they give an HIGH logic value in the absence of obstacles and a LOW logic value in their presence. In the latter case and in particular during an avoidance maneuver, to have a "stable" LOW logic value, it's necessary for the robot to remain very close to it, thus thinning the safety margins and making the system not very robust.

A.5 The leg and its servo-motor

In addition, in Figure 24, there is one header (J7) called LEG. This header is used by a servo motor, and specifically a continuous rotation servo. The seismic measurement requires a good connection of the accelerometer with the floor. The solution adopted is a three-point contact by means of two fixed and one retractable pivot. The retractable pivot acts as a "leg" whose movement is controlled by a servomechanism managed by the MUB. The leg is lifted off the ground during the robot's cruise operation, while it is lowered during the seismic data acquisition. The motor used for controlling the leg

offers bidirectional continuous rotation from 0 to 50 RPM, while it is powered by 5 Volts. Like the headers of the distance sensors, the left pin of the leg header corresponds to GND, the middle one corresponds to 5V while the right pin corresponds to the input for the control of the sensor.

A.6 Power supply unit

A power supply unit, which is used to power the circuits of the board. More specifically a Step-Down Voltage Regulator is used to convert the battery voltage (16.8 V) to 5 V, which is used by the microprocessor (Crumbuino) and the sensors of the system. The regulator is optimized to operate with minimum external component counts and also optimized to achieve low standby current. It can operate with a supply input voltage range from 4.5 to 17 Volts (Figure 25).

Figure 25: PCB layout and schematic of the power supply unit.

A.7 Monitor of Battery Voltage and communication

Header J2 is used to monitor the level of the battery voltage. This header consists of 2 pins, BATT_SW and BATT_MON. The BATT_SW is a digital signal, controlled by the digital pin 42 of Crumbuino, that goes from this specific header of the MU to another header of the DU. When the user makes this signal HIGH, then the switch that is implemented on the DU for monitoring the battery voltage activates and the battery level returns to the BATT_MON pin. By reading the BATT_MON pin (analog pin 13), the user can see the voltage of the battery divided by 4. This is helpful for deciding whether or not the robot must go for charging (Figure 26).

Figure 26: PCB layout and schematic of J2 header.

Header J17 (6-pin) used for 5 spare digital signals and 1 analog. This means that the user can use ever more pins than the ones used for the sensors. On the PCB layout is written the pin of the microcontroller, making it easy to find the right pin for programming. An *A* corresponds to an analog signal, while *D* stands for digital. For example, D11 describes that a digital signal can be connected to the Digital 11 pin (D11) of the microcontroller, while A15 means that an analog signal can be connected to the Analog 15 pin (A15) of the microcontroller (Figure 27).

Figure 27: PCB layout and schematic of J17 header.

The 4-pin header (J5) is used by a level shifter. More specifically, the MPU communicates with the DU through I2C protocol. For this reason, a voltage level shifter was also added in order to achieve the flawless communication of the two boards, since Crumbuino works with 5V while the Raspberry used by the DU works with 3V3. For the I2C communication of the boards the user has to connect the SDA and SCL signals of the Raspberry, as also 3V3 and GND of Raspberry, to the connector J5 (Figure 28).

Figure 28: PCB layout and schematic of J5 header.